

The Effect of Entrepreneurial Education on the Performance of Cooperative Business in Anambra State Polytechnic Mgbakwu, Awka, South-east, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study is on the effect of entrepreneurial education on the performance of selected cooperative businesses in Anambra state polytechnic Mgbakwu, Awka, Nigeria. The study was necessitated as a result of collapses or folding up of many cooperative businesses due to the level of competition in the contemporary turbulent and globalized environment. The broad objective was: to investigate the effect of entrepreneurial education on the performance of selected cooperatives in Anambra state polytechnics (ANSPOLY). The specific objectives were to; ascertain the effect of innovation on the performance of selected cooperatives, to examine the effect of creativity on the performance of selected cooperatives. In line with the above objectives, two hypotheses were formulated to guide the study. The study was carried out using a survey design. The population of the study was 185 from the two (2) selected cooperatives under study. A sample size of 127 was obtained from the population using sloven formula at (5% error margin). The instrument used for data collection was questionnaire structured on a 5-point Likert Scale. Designed instrument was validated through content validity using five experts from both the industry and academia. Cronbach's Alpha (0.700 – 0.872) were used to establish instrument reliability. Data were analyzed with the aid of SPSS version 23. The descriptive statistics were the mean and standard deviation, whilst the inferential statistics was a Multiple Linear Regression analysis to assess the effect of the independent variable on the dependent variable. Findings indicated that: the processed data had a significance level of 0.000, which shows that the data is ideal for concluding the population parameters as the value of significance (p-value) is less than 0.05. More so, the calculated value was greater than the critical value (16.811>3.499) which means that the null hypotheses were rejected, an indication that there was a significant effect of entrepreneurial education on the business performance of cooperative enterprises. It was also revealed that holding the Entrepreneurial Education (EE) to a constant zero, the Business Performance (BP) of cooperative enterprises would stand at 25.388. Nevertheless, the EE dimensions are as follows: a unit increase in Innovativeness (IN) would lead to an increase in BP by a factor of 0.803; with IN being significant at 0.000. Furthermore, a unit increase in Creativity (C) would significantly lead to an increase in the BP by a factor of 0.719; with PA being significant at 0.013. This shows that innovativeness and creativity have positive effect on cooperative business performance. Conclusively it is very vital for cooperative enterprises to have their entrepreneurial education (EE) fortified as this study has shown that overall, entrepreneurial education has a significant effect on business performance. The study recommends that entrepreneurial development initiative that aims at building the EE dimensions of cooperative enterprises, should focus on innovativeness and creativity.

Keywords: Cooperative Business; Entrepreneurial Education; Performance; Anambra State Polytechnic

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Background of the Study

Cooperative organisations are business enterprises with a dual objective of promoting the social and economic well-being of their members (Onugu, Usman & Moore, 2019). Egor, Chilokwu and Owan, (2015) stated that various types of cooperative societies exist such as Consumer cooperatives, housing cooperatives, worker cooperatives, Credit coop. etc. They maintained that Farmers' Multipurpose Cooperative societies play a dynamic role in the socio-economic development of the nation. However, cooperatives have common small-scale businesses apart from the member-patron business economic unit; they noted that the performance of these small-scale enterprises of the cooperatives goes a long way to show the extent of sustainability of the cooperatives in Nigeria. Nwachukwu and Onuoha (2022) posited that Performance of organizations plays a crucial role in boosting the firms competitiveness, resilience, effectiveness, sustainability and efficiency. Egor, Chilokwu and Owan (2015) pointed out that cooperative society is not an end in itself, but a means to achieve certain goals. One of the primary goals of a cooperative society is the advancement of the members' economic interests, protecting and maintaining the economic independence of the small entrepreneurs by balancing economic weakness through the pooling of resources and thus achieving economies of scale.

Miller (1983), as cited in Rezaei & Ortt (2018), asserted that one of the most widely used constructs to assess firm's entrepreneurship is entrepreneurial orientation (EO). A firm is considered to be entrepreneurial if it is innovative, proactive creative and risk-taking. Entrepreneurial education enhances the specific characteristics, basic skills and trait of an entrepreneur which are relevant in managing business establishment in tackling challenges encountered by the organization in order to enhance its growth and survivability. An organisation's entrepreneurial procedure may be helpful in taking advantage of new entry opportunities, which is relevant in boosting its performance (Nwachukwu & Onuoha, 2022). Many cooperative businesses are no longer viable because of several factors, such as non-attendance at meetings, poor record-keeping and poor entrepreneurial orientation, which includes innovativeness, proactiveness, creativity and risk-taking. The success of cooperative businesses often depends on the ability to manage the challenges that could affect the establishment's success. Hence, the education of an entrepreneur is very relevant in enhancing the performance of the cooperative business.

However, not much research has been carried out on entrepreneurial education and the performance of cooperative business. It is against this background that the researchers intend to investigate the influence of entrepreneurial education on the performance of cooperative societies in Anambra State Polytechnic, Mgbakwu.

Objectives of the Study

The broad objective was: To investigate the effect of entrepreneurial education on the performance of selected cooperatives in Anambra state polytechnics (ANSPOLY).

The specific objectives were:

1. To ascertain the effect of innovation on the performance of selected cooperatives,
2. To examine the effect of creativity on the performance of selected cooperatives

Hypotheses of the Study

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between innovativeness and the performance of cooperative enterprises in Anspoly

H₀₂: There is no significant relationship between creativity and the performance of cooperative enterprises in Anspoly

Conceptual Review

Cooperative Society

Cooperative Societies Act 1993, as cited in Norliana et al. (2019), a Cooperative is an establishment, comprised of individuals with the purpose to increase the economic and social benefits, especially among its members, in accordance with the cooperative's principles. The International Cooperative Alliance (ICA) 1995; defined cooperative as "an autonomous association of persons united voluntarily to meet their common economic, social and cultural needs and aspirations through a jointly owned and democratically controlled enterprise." The International Cooperative Alliance (ICA) outlines these seven (7) principles of cooperatives, namely; (1) voluntary and open

membership, (2) democratic member control, (3) member economic participation, (4) autonomy and independence, (5) education, training and information, (6) cooperation among cooperatives, and (7) concern for community (International Co-operative Alliance, 2012). Hence, these principles become a solid foundation for cooperative entrepreneurs to remain in facing business challenges

Performance

The organizational performance is a benchmark or an indicator for efficiency, effectiveness, and environmental obligation like productivity, time of cycle, reduction of waste, and compliance of rules (Muchira 2013, as cited in Alshehhi, Bhaumik & Alshibami, 2019). Omhonria and Needorn (2022) posited that firms performance depict the degree at which a corporate entity achieved its missions as it relates with work outcome, customers relationship, quality service and overall wellbeing). Lebens and Euske (2006) offer a series of concepts that explain the idea of organizational performance where they opined that performance is a collection of financial and non-financial metrics that provide details about the degree to which goals and outcomes are accomplished. Performance can be explained using a causal model, which explains how current behaviour will influence future outcomes. The large amount of definitions serve to view the performance of the organizations as a tool for achieving objectives (Shahzad, Luqman, Rashid Khan & Shabbir, 2012 as cited in Talal, et al.,2019).

Entrepreneurship Education

Entrepreneurship Education is the acquisition of knowledge, skills, abilities and competencies which enable individuals/students to be independent, leading to the creation of new jobs and business on their own which is necessary for societal development. Jacob and Ariya (2015) defined entrepreneurship education as the type of education which assists students to think creatively in order to acquire knowledge, develop desirable attitudes and skills for self-reliance. Entrepreneurship education is a kind of education which aims at assisting students to develop positive attitudes, innovative skills for self-reliance, rather than relying on the government for employment (Henry et al., 2005 as cited in Boahemaah, Xin, Dobge, & Pomegbe, 2020).

According to Paul (2005) and Oborah (2006), the objectives of entrepreneurship education include the following:

1. To provide meaningful education to the youth, which will make them become self-reliant and subsequently encourage them to derive profit and become self-dependent.
2. Provide graduates with the training and support necessary to help them establish a career in small and medium-sized businesses.
3. Offer institution graduates with enough training that will enable them to be creative
4. Provide the graduates with training in skills that will make them meet the manpower needs of society.
5. Provide graduates with enough training in risk management to make uncertainty bearing possible and easy.

However, the essence of entrepreneurship education is to produce entrepreneurs who can make use of their initiative and innovative skills to invent businesses and manage them in order to escape the dangers of poverty and the frustration of employment (Atakpa, 2016).

Innovativeness

Schumpeter 1935, as cited in Yermias, Moeljadi, & Ratna, 2019) defined innovation as the adoption of a new product or process. Covin and Slevin 1989, as cited in Nwachukwu & Onuoha, 2022) describe innovativeness as an organisation's proclivity for idea creation, experimentation, and research and development. Additionally, innovativeness is described as a business's capacity and willingness to pursue novel ideas or to innovate and develop procedures that result in new goods. Covin and Miles (1999) concur that entrepreneurship cannot survive without innovativeness and that innovativeness is a critical component of company survival strategies. An innovation can be new to the company, new to a market, a country or a region, or new globally. Innovations are new creations (in material form) that have significant economic value, typically developed by companies or individuals through the introduction of a new product or process (Yermias et al., 2019).

Creativity

Neely and Hii (1998, as cited in Juliana, Hui, Clement, Solomon, and Elvis, 2021) described Creativity as an individual's ability to come up with fresh and original ideas to achieve a purpose. The application of creativity to find a solution to a problem is known as innovation. This simply means that creativity is a means of problem-solving. It is the application of a new approach, new concept, product, or method to increase a system's effectiveness or performance.

Creativity is described as the ability to invent or otherwise bring something new into being, whether it's a new approach to a problem, a new method or device, or a new object or form of art. On the other hand, Sart (2013) describes creativity as something unique and useful. Creativity is the act of seeing something that everyone else does but connecting it in ways that no one else has. Creativity is shifting from the familiar to the unfamiliar (Juliana et al., 2021).

Theoretical Framework

The major theory that was chosen for this research is the Knowledge-Based View, also regarded as the Knowledge-Based Theory (KBT), which emphasises the knowledge of entrepreneurs or small business owners as the main resource needed for good performance. Conner (1991) was the first to historically compare the Resource-Based Theory and five schools of thought within industrial organisation economics and suggested the Knowledge-Based Theory as a new theory. Grant (1996), amongst other scholars at the time, provided a detailed exposition of the firm's Knowledge Based Theory. Grant (1996) proposes that the establishment of heterogeneous knowledge structures across a firm's management hierarchies is a necessary condition for achieving long-term knowledge-based competitive advantage. Other KBT proponents argued that because knowledge-based resources are typically difficult to imitate and are socially complex, heterogeneous knowledge bases and capabilities among firms are the primary determinants of sustained competitive advantage and superior corporate performance (Curado & Bontis, 2006).

Empirical Review

Irikefe and Bagobiri, (2022) investigated the effect of EO on the performance of small enterprises in Abuja, Nigeria. The objective of the study was to specifically assess the effect of the dimensions of EO viz. autonomy, innovativeness, proactiveness and risk taking on the business performance of small enterprises in Abuja. The study made use of a survey research design to target a population of 2750 small enterprises in Abuja. Using the Taro Yamane formula, a sample size of 349 was obtained. Out of the 349 questionnaires randomly issued to the small enterprises, 338 were completed and returned, representing a 96.84% response rate. The questionnaires contained closed-ended questions that were rated on a 5-point Likert scale. The data was analyzed using descriptive statistics and multiple linear regression. Arising from the result, the regression model was significant at 0.000 with the calculated value greater than the critical value ($16.910 > 2.399$), hence, the null hypothesis was rejected. It was concluded that, overall, EO has a significant effect on business performance. However, of the dimensions tested, autonomy is insignificant, while innovativeness, proactiveness and risk-taking are significant. The study recommends that entrepreneurial development initiative that aims at building the EO dimensions of small enterprises should focus on innovativeness, proactiveness and risk-taking, rather than autonomy.

Zannah and Mahar (2021) investigated the impact of innovation, risk taking, and proactiveness on the success of small and medium businesses. In addition, the microfinance institution plays a moderating function. A total of 340 surveys were sent to SMEs' owners and managers, with 308 being returned satisfactorily. Entrepreneurs improve the success of small and medium businesses through innovating, taking risks, and being proactive. The data is analyzed using the descriptive statistic Pearson correlation analysis. The findings reveal a strong and favorable connection between EO (innovation, risk-taking, and proactiveness) and the success of Nigeria's small and medium-sized businesses. Only innovation and proactiveness were shown to be statistically significant predictors of small and medium-sized businesses in Nigeria, whereas risk-taking was found to be statistically insignificant.

Nwangwu, et al. (2020) looked at the impact of innovativeness on youth economic empowerment, as well as the impact of risk-taking capacity and change orientation on youth economic empowerment. The study used a survey research design and a quantitative research method. All 321 registered sachet water businesses in Anambra state were included in the target population. Purposive/judgmental sampling was used to choose 321 respondents from the population. The research received a good response, with a response rate of 96.88 percent (311). The hypotheses were tested using multiple regression analysis. Risk-taking has a substantial beneficial impact on adolescent economic

empowerment, according to the research. Change orientation has a substantial beneficial impact on young economic empowerment, according to the research.

Methodology

The study adopted the survey research design, which relies on responses obtained from primary data. The population of the study comprised of the two cooperative societies in Anambra State Polytechnic, with a membership strength of 185 and this was also used to calculate the sample size using the sloven formula:

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2}$$

Where: n = sample size; N = population; e = degree of error expected. With a degree of error expected at 0.05 and a population at 185 it brings the proposed sample size to about 127 as computed below:

$$n = \frac{185}{1 + 185(0.05)^2}$$

$$n = \frac{185}{1 + 185(0.0025)}$$

$$n = \frac{185}{1 + 0.4625}$$

$$n = \frac{185}{1.4625}$$

$$n = 126.495 \approx 127$$

The sample size is: 127

Stratified Sampling Technique

Stratified Sampling technique was applied to determine the sample proportion of the respondents in each of the cooperatives in ANSPOLY. The stratified sample is as follows using the Bowley's allocation formula; $n_h = nN_h/N$

Therefore

Table 1: Anambra State Polytechnic, Mgbakwu

S/N	Cooperative Society	SAMPLE SIZE
1	Anspoly Mgbakwu multipurpose cooperative society Ltd	96(127) 185 = 66
2	Anspoly Mgbakwu staff cooperative thrift and investment society Ltd	89(127) 185 = 61
	TOTAL	127

Source: Researcher's Computation, 2024

The administered surveys were tested to confirm their reliability. The method used for testing for the internal consistency was Cronbach's Alpha, which is computed with the model:

$$\alpha = \frac{Nr}{1 + r(N - 1)}$$

Where: α = Cronbach Alonpha; N = the number of items in the scale; r = the mean inter-item correlation.

Table 2: Result of Reliability Test

Variables	Number of Items	Cronbach's Alpha Coefficient
Effect of Innovativeness (IN)	5	0.75
Effect of Creativity (CT)	4	0.74
Business Performance (BP)	3	0.72

Source: Researchers' Computation, 2024

In the context of this research, the levels of alpha values were higher than the 0.7 thresholds that were regarded as reliable—Cronbach’s Alpha > 0.70. SPSS version 23 was used to analyse the primary data. The descriptive statistics were the mean and standard deviation, whilst the inferential statistics was a Multiple Linear Regression analysis to assess the influence of the independent variable on the dependent variable. The statistical model used was:

$$y = a + bx + \varepsilon \quad (1)$$

This is specified thus as: $BP = \alpha + \beta_1IN + \beta_2CT + \varepsilon \quad (2)$

Where, BP = Business performance (Dependent variable);

IN = Innovativeness (independent variable 1);

CT = Creativity (independent variable 2);

α = Intercept or constant; β = Coefficient; the slope of the regression line with respect to the independent variables; ε = Error term

Data Presentation and Analysis

Descriptive Statistics

To establish the effect of Entrepreneurial Education (EE) on the Business Performance (BP) of cooperative enterprises, Survey instrument for the collection of data was developed for the study using a 5-point Likert scale ranked thus; Strongly Agree (SA) 5, Agree (A) 4, Undecided (UD)3, Disagree (D)2, Strongly Disagree (SD) 1. The gathered responses were analysed using means and standard deviations to demonstrate the diversity of individual replies from the aggregate mean of the responses for each variable of the research

Multiple Linear Regression Analysis

The model and hypotheses were tested at a 0.05 significance level. Table 4.1. shows a model summary that is used to measure how well the regression model fits the data.

Table 3: Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Standard Error of the Estimate
1	0.735a	0.540	0.536	2.298

a. Predictors: (Constant), IN, CT, Source: Researchers’ Computation, 2023

As shown in Table 3, the Multiple R of 0.735 indicates a strong linear effect on the independent variable (Entrepreneurial Education (EE)) and the dependent variable (Business Performance (BP)). The model also has an R Square of 0.540, meaning that the independent variable explains 54.0% of the variability of the dependent variable—it further shows that other proxies that may affect the business performance (BP) of cooperative enterprises, not tested in the study, amount to about 46.0%. The Adjusted R Square was 0.536, an indication that there was a variation of 53.6% in the Business Performance of cooperative enterprises due to changes in their Entrepreneurial Education. The Standard Error of the Estimate shows that the observed values fall an average of 2.298 units from the regression line

Table 4: Analysis of Variance (ANOVA)

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	261.764	2	65.676	16.811	0.000 ^b
Residual	1,273.705	127	3.865	—	—
Total	1,546.489	129	—	—	—

a. Dependent Variable: BP

b. Predictors: (Constant), IN, CT

Source: Researchers’ Computation, 2023

From the ANOVA table (Table 4), the processed data had a significance level of 0.000, which shows that the data is ideal for concluding the population parameters as the value of significance (p-value) is less than 0.05. More so, the

calculated value was greater than the critical value (16.811>3.499), an indication that there was a significant effect of entrepreneurial education on the business performance of cooperative enterprises

Table 5: Coefficient of Determination

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients (B)	Std. Error	Standardized Coefficients (Beta)	t	Sig.
(Constant)	25.388	2.886	—	8.796	0.000
Innovativeness (IN)	0.803	0.211	1.004	3.803	0.000
Creativity (CT)	0.719	0.167	0.935	4.305	0.013

a. Dependent Variable: BP

Source: Researchers' Computation, 2023

From Table 5, and in line with Equation (2), the statistical model could be represented as: $25.388 = \alpha + 0.803IN + 0.719PA + \epsilon$. Following Table 5, it was revealed that holding the Entrepreneurial Education (EE) to a constant zero, the Business Performance (BP) of cooperative enterprises would stand at 25.388. Nevertheless, the EO dimensions are as follows: A unit increase in Innovation (IN) would lead to an increase in BP by a factor of 0.803, with IN being significant at 0.000. Furthermore, a unit increase in Creativity (CT) would significantly lead to an increase in the BP by a factor of 0.719; with PA being significant at 0.013. This shows that innovativeness has the leading positive effect on small enterprises' business performance, followed by Creativity

Table 6: Summary of Hypotheses

Hypothesis Statement	Model	Result
H_{01} : There is no significant relationship between innovativeness and the performance of cooperative enterprises in Anspoly	$EP = \alpha + \beta_2 IN + \epsilon$	$p < 0.05$ — Rejected
H_{02} : There is no significant relationship between creativity and the performance of cooperative enterprises in Anspoly	$EP = \alpha + \beta_3 PA + \epsilon$	$p < 0.05$ — Rejected

Source: Researchers' Result, 2024

From Table 6, the null hypothesis was rejected in favour of the alternative hypotheses

Conclusions

It is vital for cooperative enterprises to have their entrepreneurial Education (EE) fortified, as this study has shown that entrepreneurial education has a significant effect on business performance. The result of the study indicates that innovativeness and creativity have a positive effect on cooperative enterprises' business performance. Consequently, it can be concluded from this study that there is a strong association between innovativeness and creativity domains of EE, such that a cooperative enterprise with a good drive for innovation will also likely be very creative.

Recommendations

The study recommends that an entrepreneurial development initiative that aims at building the EE dimensions of cooperative enterprises should focus on innovativeness and creativity.

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